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Major shortcomings of the first WHO-recommended RT-qPCR to “detect” SARS-CoV-2 and to “diagnose” Covid-19.

NGS provides evidence that successive waves of SARS-CoV-2 variants lack genomic relationship.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction For the first time in medical history, the result of a laboratory assay, here RT-qPCR, was used as the sole criterion to diagnose a disease, namely Covid-19, without any rating of clinical symptoms and to justify the implementation of population-wide non-pharmaceutical interventions during virus season.

Objectives (1) To summarize concerns raised within the scientific community on the first WHO-recommended RT-qPCR protocol to detect SARS-CoV-2 sequences; (2) To genomically characterize individual SARS-CoV-2 strains circulating in the Czech Republic from autumn 2020 to spring 2021 applying next generation sequencing; (3) To re-initiate the currently missing scientific dialogue and return to reason and evidence-based medicine.

Results Neglected principles of good scientific practice resulted not only in the publication of the WHO-recommended Charité RT-qPCR protocol, but also in multiple health-related problems. On the one hand, unnecessary quarantine of false positive-tested, but healthy individuals, as well as lockdowns and atrocious collateral damage on societies and economies worldwide due to a high number of false-positive “PCR-cases.” On the other hand, some chain of infection caused by false negative-tested, but symptomatic individuals lead to real Covid-19 clusters. Based on the genomic mutation profile of SARS-CoV-2, we were able to demonstrate that the three individual waves culminating from autumn 2020 to spring 2021 were successive, but lacked direct genomic relationship between each other. This became obvious with the omicron variant, which did not reveal direct evolutionary connection to any of the previous SARS-CoV-2 variants.

Conclusions Both our own results and data from available literature confirmed that validation of any PCR-based diagnostic test by sequencing is mandatory, not only during the initial phase of establishment, but also on a regular basis during the following time. To prevent future misconduct, science needs a reality check and must re-initiate the scientific dialogue and liberate itself from political influence and dogma.

Keywords: Charité protocol, Covid-19, next generation sequencing (NGS), RT-qPCR, SARS-CoV-2, scientific misconduct

Introduction

Since March 2020, Covid-19 (Coronavirus disease 2019) keeps the world on edge mostly due to collateral damage with a catastrophic impact on health, society and economies. Remarkably, right from the beginning of the putative pandemic – and for the first time in medical history – there was a global political consensus that disease status, infection and infectivity could be diagnosed solely by a RT-qPCR (Reverse Transcription – quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction) laboratory assay independent of any clinical symptoms of the tested individual. Due to the critical importance of the test result, one could readily anticipate that the highest quality standards for test accuracy and reliability were adopted. However, in this paper, we question the most frequently used RT-qPCR laboratory assay for mass testing on this matter.

Timeline of the Covid-19 pandemic On December 30th 2019, a hospital in the Chinese city of Wuhan reported that seven of their patients suffered from a severe pneumonia of unknown origin [1]. The local health authorities immediately informed the WHO (World Health Organization) and already identified the causative agent as a coronavirus applying whole genome sequencing and RT-PCR [2]. On January 7th 2020, the identified virus was named 2019-nCoV (2019 novel CoronaVirus) and later was renamed to SARS-CoV-2 (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome–CoronaVirus-2) due to strong homologies with SARS-CoV [3]. Subsequently, the CCDC (Chinese Center of Disease Control) reported that they had established a RT-qPCR assay to detect the novel virus in patient samples [4]. Sequencing results revealed that the identified virus belongs to the beta-Coronaviridae of the subgenus Sarbecoviruses. On January 9th 2020, the Chinese scientists shared their findings with the WHO [5] and uploaded the full-length virus sequence into the GISAID database (NC_045512.1). The WHO published the first diagnostic RT-qPCR test protocol online on January 13th 2020 [6]. Remarkably, the published RT-qPCR test guidelines were not based on the protocols established and shared by the Chinese scientists, but was a product of several cooperating laboratories in Europe [7]. They used the Wuhan sequences deposited in the GISAID database by the CCDC [5] for primer and probe design without any positive patient samples or the virus itself being available to validate the test [8]. The European protocol recommended three targets (located in the nucleocapsid (N) gene, the envelope (E) gene and corresponding to the RNA-dependent RNA-polymerase (RdRp) from the ORF1ab gene) and was intended to detect the whole Sarbeco subgroup with one RdRp probe as discriminating oligonucleotide only. This enabled the use of the SARS-CoV strain Frankfurt-1 as a positive control, however, proof of accuracy of the amplified targets by proper controls and sequencing were not shown. On January 17th 2020, an update was published on the WHO webpage correcting the former protocol by omitting the most specific primer pair for the N-gene target

due to “lack of sensitivity” [9]. Six days later, on January 23rd 2020, this RT-qPCR protocol, which quickly became the standard for the detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in Europe and many other countries, was published as a research manuscript by Eurosurveillance after an alleged full peer-review process that took only one day [8]. The primers and probes from the Charite-protocol were made commercially available very hastily, as a laboratory in Slovenia reported that “after extensive evaluation, our laboratory implemented LightMix-based SARS-CoV-2 testing on January 17th 2020” - at a time when there was not a single case in Europe [10].

On January 30th 2020, the WHO Emergency Commission declared the disease outbreak a PHEIC (Public Health Emergency of International Concern) [11], but the assessment of the situation was based on as few as 1,651 test-positive cases in China including 38 deaths, and 98 cases in 18 countries outside China without any reported deaths [12]. On March 11th 2020, the number of test-positive SARS-CoV-2 cases had risen to 4,670 worldwide, including 280 deaths attributed to this new virus-induced disease Covid-19 [12] and the WHO Director-General, Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, declared Covid-19 a pandemic [13]. This was possible in agreement with the weakened WHO definition of a pandemic, as rephrased in 2009, which did no longer require “enormous numbers of deaths and illness” [14].

WHO strategy to combat the Covid-19 pandemic On March 16th 2020, Dr. Ghebreyesus announced the global strategy for handling Covid-19: “We have a simple message to all countries: test, test, test. Test every suspected case. If they test positive, isolate them and find out with whom they have been in close contact, up to two days before they developed symptoms, and test those people too [15].” In parallel, the WHO launched the Covid-19 dashboard feature allowing real-time tracking of RT-qPCR positive test results in absolute numbers independent of the number of tests performed and without further specifying the test system applied. This was intended to support planning, implementation and resourcing of country preparedness and response activities – on the basis of worldwide 13,982 RT-qPCR positive cases including 871 Covid-19 attributed deaths [12]. The strategy recommended by the WHO to test as many people as possible independent of clinical symptoms by this technology seems puzzling, as RT-qPCR technically is neither able to verify an infectious pathogen like a virus and thus identify a contagious person (see below), nor to diagnose a disease. PCR technology just amplifies any genetic material of interest, i.e., small parts of a viral genome like that from SARS-CoV-2, independent of the “viability” of the source. Further, page 9 of a Consensus Document on the Epidemiology of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) [16], a highly related virus, reads as follows: “Data linkage is required to determine whether there is a direct relationship between clinical severity and viral load and excretion.” This implies that a RT-qPCR positively tested individual cannot be automatically considered to be or become symptomatic or infectious without correct allocation to clinical symptoms.

Therefore, it is incomprehensible that the WHO committed to the RT-qPCR test strategy even after publication of a systematic review demonstrating that patient characteristics (i.e., severity of symptoms) and test parameters (i.e., cycle threshold) strictly determines the reliability of the RT-qPCR test result [17]. Furthermore, the WHO must have been aware of the pitfalls connected to PCR testing, as in 2006, false-positive results caused a pseudo-pandemic of the whooping cough in the Dartmouth-Hitchcock Medical Center [18]. Nevertheless, mass testing by RT-qPCR became the strategy of choice to monitor Covid-19 and, from this time on, the number of positive tests was used to justify massive restrictions of human rights and nationwide lockdowns.

As a plethora of scientists, physicians and medical advisors have reported their complaints on the shortcomings of the first WHO-recommended RT-qPCR, we further challenged the seminal protocol for the detection of SARS-CoV-2, hereafter referred to as the Charité protocol [8]. Based on the inter-individual genomic heterogeneity of the SARS-CoV-2 strains alpha, beta, gamma and omicron [19], we identified a unique region located in the 3'-UTR as a both specific and sensitive target for real-time RT-qPCR detection of SARS-CoV-2 related RNA. Subsequently, we characterized the genome sequences of individual SARS-CoV-2 strains that circulated in the Czech Republic from autumn 2020 to spring 2021. Moreover, we address critical comments raised within the scientific community following a retraction request for the Charité protocol [20] and discuss in a review-based manner the major concerns that accompanies the Charité protocol and how the politicization of science breeches the principles of good scientific practice and has affected societies worldwide.

Methods

Ethics statement Samples for routine molecular diagnostics were taken upon informed consent and due to governmental legal directive in regards to the Covid-19 pandemic testing strategy, issued and archived by the referring Clinics. Anonymized samples were processed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (<https://www.wma.net/what-we-do/medical-ethics/declaration-of-helsinki/>).

Primer design targeting the 5'-UTR region of SARS-CoV-2 for RT-qPCR Using sequence alignment of genomic sequences available in February 2020 relative to Bat/SARS/nCoV-19 coronaviruses, we selected a unique region located in the conserved 5'-UTR of SARS-CoV-2 to serve as a specific and sensitive target for real-time RT-qPCR detection of the viral RNA resulting in a 207 bp amplicon. We validated the assay in-house, according to the European ISO 13485 guidelines for the production of in-vitro diagnostics. 50 positive cases identified in

authentic symptomatic patient samples (nasopharyngeal swabs), were confirmed by direct Sanger sequencing of the obtained PCR products. The assay fulfilled all requirements for specificity (no false-specific products observed) and sensitivity (seven copies of the targets in a PCR reaction). In addition, our assay underwent external validation by the UK NEQAS official authority for quality assessment and, subsequently, deployed into routine diagnostics with 30K plus authentic samples tested so far.

Characteristics of primers and probe are summarized in **Table 1**. The PCR profile was an initial denaturation step at 94 °C for 5 min, followed by 45 cycles at 94 °C for 30 sec, at 58 °C for 30 sec (acquiring at FAM) and at 72 °C for 30 sec.

Table 1 Diagnostic primer-set and TaqMan hybridization probe for routine SARS-CoV-2 real-time qPCR, as performed at TILIA LABORATORIES from March 2020 to April 2022. Given the intrinsic genomic stability of the 5'-UTR region of coronaviruses, the assay did not require any redesign despite the various SARS-CoV-2 strains emerging since March 2020. Tm and GC-content values of oligonucleotides are as calculated by the manufacturer (Eurofins Genomics, Germany).

Oligo name	Sequence 5'-3'	Tm [°C]	GC [%]
5'-UTRforward	CGATCTCTTGTAGATCTGTTCTC	58.9	43
5'-UTRreverse	CACCCGGACGAAACCTAGATGTGC	66.1	58
5'-UTR TaqMan probe	FAM-TACTGTCGTTGACAGGACACGAGTAACTCGTCT-BHQ1	70.6	48

The identity of amplicons was confirmed by Sanger sequencing and no false-positive signals were observed, which indicated absolute specificity of the assay, so that all positive cases were reported. The copy number of the virus per ml of the initial sample eluate was calculated using calibration curve constructed from 4 log dilutions of a synthetic genomic sequence covering the 5'-UTR sequence and its immediate flanking region (customs-synthesized by Eurofins Genomics, Germany).

In contrast to the WHO-recommended Charité protocol - recommending 45 cycles without defining a Ct for positive/negative discrimination, but resulting in a high rate of false-positives at Ct > 35 (see below) – our 5'-UTR assay clearly outperformed the Charité protocol in terms of specificity (no non-specific PCR products even when applying 45 cycles), while retaining the necessary sensitivity. As the regulatory 5'-UTR inherently remains stable in coronaviruses, which is also the case with SARS-CoV-2, we were able to use our 5'-UTR assay successfully throughout the pandemic irrespective of the downstream genomic heterogeneity of the individual circulating strains observed over time. The 5'-UTR assay is distinguished by no false background (e.i., a negative sample is really PCR negative). Thus, any positivity, with explicitly calculated SARS-CoV-2 copy numbers, have been reported to the clinicians. Given the years-long history of real-time quantitative PCR analytics in our country, the clinicians have already been well versed in interpreting the data, from unremarkable viral loads (10e1-10e2 copies per

ml) to moderate viral loads (10^3 – 10^4 copies per ml) up to remarkable and highly remarkable viral loads (10^5 – 10^9 copies per ml).

Molecular tracing of the SARS-CoV-2 circulating strains in the Czech Republic We genomically characterized 260 authentic SARS-CoV-2 samples from symptomatic individuals (no detailed clinical data available) collected between September 2020 and April 2021 using Sanger sequencing and fragment analysis of the SARS-CoV-2 S-protein gene, which allowed us to distinguish three distinct genomic clusters of SARS-CoV-2 that directly correspond to the individual “waves” (**Figure 1**). Primers used for the genotyping of the individual SARS-CoV-2 strains, applicable for all circulating strains), were the following:

SARS-CoV-2 forward: CACACGTGGTGTATTACCCTGAC

SARS-CoV-2 delta-reverse: FAM-TCAAAAGTGCAATTATTCGCACTAG

SARS-CoV-2 UK-forward: GTAATTAGAGGTGATGAAGTCAGAC

SARS-Sars-CoV-2 UK-reverse: CCACAAACAGTTGCTGGTGCATGTAG

From each of the three clusters (September 2020, November 2020, December 2020), we selected four random representatives and subjected them to NGS whole genome sequencing (SRA Bioproject, accession no. PRJNA742374).

Whole genome sequencing of SARS-CoV-2 isolates using NGS Whole RNA was isolated from authentic patient samples, using QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit (Qiagen, Germany), according to the manufacturer’s recommendations. Total RNA was reversely transcribed using Verso cDNA kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and tailing products covering the whole SARS-CoV-2 genome were PCR amplified using the ARTIC v3 primers (IDT, USA). Obtained PCR pools (fragments of approximately 400 bp) were gel-purified using QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (Qiagen, Germany) and subjected to NGS library building using NEBNext® Fast DNA Library Prep Set for Ion Torrent kit (NEB, USA), according to the manufacturer’s instructions. Libraries were quantified applying Ion Plus Fragment Library kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and 10 pM library pool was used as a template for emulsion PCR (emPCR) using Ion PGM™ Hi-Q™ View OT2 Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). After bead enrichment (OT2 instrument, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), a v316 NGS sequencing chip was loaded in order to obtain sufficient base coverage. NGS sequencing was performed applying the Ion Torrent PGM platform (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) using the Ion PGM™ Hi-Q™ View Sequencing Kit chemistry (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Raw data obtained were end- and quality-trimmed and used for direct alignment with the SARS-CoV-2 reference genome (MT192773) to identify genomic mutations characteristic for the September, November and December 2020 waves.

Literature review On November 27th 2020, an international consortium of 22 scientists (including UK. PB, RJK and KS of this paper) submitted an external review report [20] together with a retraction request for Corman et al. [8] to the Eurosurveillance Editorial Board. As documents were, in parallel, placed online on both a scientific preprint server and researchgate.net, the scientific community provided both additional references and reasonable criticism concerning the lack of wet-lab experimental data supporting the raised concerns. This information was summarized in an addendum and submitted to Eurosurveillance on January 11th 2021. All documents are available online [20]. Here, we summarize the major shortcomings of the first WHO-recommended RT-qPCR protocol, but also add new findings published since then.

Results

Given the fact that the Charité protocol suffered from a high non-specific background producing false-positive results above a Ct-value of 35 for all target regions and such a suboptimal design cannot be employed in routine diagnostics, we rejected the Charité design and instead established a new assay, hereafter referred to as 5'-UTR assay. While the Charité protocol recommends amplification of three target sequences located within the E-gene, the RdRp-gene and the N-gene, our 5'-UTR assay targets only one, but highly conserved sequence within the 5'-UTR of SARS-CoV-2. This design proved to be 100% specific without any unspecific background, as corroborated by Sanger sequencing of the obtained PCR amplicons.

An additional advantage of our 5'-UTR assay over the Charité protocol is that the 5'-UTR represents a stable region in coronaviruses in contrast to the downstream genes that are prone to mutations [21]. Using our 5'-UTR assay, we could reliably diagnose all SARS-CoV-2 positive individuals irrespective of the circulating strain (i.e., alpha, beta, gamma, delta, omicron). The high mutation rate of SARS-CoV-2 often disqualified the Charité-based protocols from reliable diagnostic use and more than one diagnostic target (Orf-, N-, S-, E-gene) was needed to be able to cover all circulating strains and to reduce the rate of false-positives found with every single target due to the problematic test design. However, this was not the case with our 5'-UTR assay, which targeted one highly conserved sequence of the SARS-CoV-2 genome that has been stable since March 2020 and easily detects even heavily mutated SARS-CoV-2 variants, such as omicron.

Using genomic follow-up and NGS whole genome sequencing of random representatives from each of the three autumn 2020 waves, we were able to demonstrate that each wave was represented by a different SARS-CoV-2 strain. Indeed, mutations found in the September 2020 wave were not present in the directly following November 2020 and December 2020 waves (aka "British", "B.1.1.7.", or later on "alpha"). The disparity is most prominent between the

September 2020 and the November 2020 SARS-CoV-2 strain, when the November wave “lost” 14 mutations present in the preceding September wave (**Figure 1**).

Discussion and Literature Review

The authors of the Charité protocol, which served as a blueprint for most of the subsequent protocols at least in Europe, aimed (in the abstract) “to develop and deploy a robust diagnostic methodology enabling its use in a public health laboratory setting without having virus material available [8].” The proposed objective, however, could never be achieved due to the following aspects: Firstly, to establish a reliable diagnostic method, specific biological material (here, the virus of interest) must be available in order to prove for specificity and sensitivity of the test design. This was not addressed in the Charite protocol, but in the protocol by the CCDC [2,3]. Secondly, a proper test design respecting international standards is mandatory. This includes highly specific test material (here, primers and probes) designed and checked for maximum specificity without cross-reactivity, as well as a robust nature in order to work with different test systems. Again, this was not addressed in the Charité protocol, as the primer design allowed for a group-specific detection of different coronaviruses. This includes a narrow cut-off window for the Ct-value determined in relation to a well-defined, specific viral load control, which has not been communicated for any of the different target genes for this protocol. Thirdly, the need for the Charité protocol was per se questionable, as the CCDC already established a well-working RT-qPCR protocol on January 3rd 2020 including specific control samples [4,22]. Fourthly, Chinese scientists had already shared the whole genome sequence of the Wuhan virus with the WHO on January 5th 2020 [23], thus allowing the establishment of highly specific primers and probes. By contrast, the Charité protocol and primer design was based on a set of synthetic sequences and the SARS-CoV strain Frankfurt-1 as a positive control without even verifying the PCR products by sequencing. Finally, a SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) including the definition of proper controls, which should have been mandatory for a “robust diagnostic test,” was not and still is not published. Although addition of this information would have been appropriate, it will not solve the key problem. RT-qPCR solely detects RNA and, by technical nature, cannot discern between “active,” intact and potentially infectious virus particles and “inactive,” harmless virus genome fragments (see below) and consequently cannot serve as a valuable diagnostic tool by itself to identify contagious individuals probably spreading the virus. Subsequently, this was confirmed in respect to the SARS-CoV-2 RT-qPCR both by M. Koopmans (co-author of the Charité protocol) in a Podcast from November 26th 2020 [24] and by A. Fauci (chief medical advisor to President Biden, USA) in a TV interview from December 30th 2021 [25].

Assessment of the infectious viral load by cell culture, not by PCR

Previous contact with a specific virus can be checked by immunological tests, which search for the host's immune response triggered by the virus of interest through the detection of specific antibodies (i.e., IgM, IgG, IgA). From the beginning of Covid-19, politicians worldwide have clearly not adopted such a policy, but instead promoted molecular tests detecting viral RNA applying RT-qPCR or, later during the pandemic, viral protein using rapid antigen tests. PCR represents a highly sensitive technique for DNA amplification originally intended to multiply specific sequences (i.e., genes) from very small sample amounts within a short time. RT-PCR for the detection of RNA targets is different from PCR, as it requires reverse transcription of RNA into DNA, which then can be subjected to PCR. In case of quantitative PCR (qPCR), as it is used for SARS-CoV-2 gene amplification, a third primer, the so-called probe, is labelled with a fluorescent dye and specifically binds within the amplified target sequence. Upon destruction of the probe by polymerase during the elongation step, a light signal is produced, which is used as a surrogate marker for amplification rounds [26,27].

Importantly, sample preparation prior to PCR – similarly, this applies also for rapid antigen tests – always requires complete break-up of any biological structures in order to separate nucleic acids, proteins, lipids and cell debris. Consequently, any PCR, even if performed properly, can solely prove for the presence of the genetic target in question, but not for the “viability” of the underlying pathogen. Therefore, PCR can by no means serve as a gold standard to assess the infectiousness of an individual.

The gold standard for determining infectiousness and infectious viral load is represented by the reproducibility of the virus of interest in cell culture [28,29,30]. Sparsely more information on a possible replication activity of a virus within a tested individual may be provided by a RT-qPCR assay that is based on the detection of subgenomic RNAs, which will solely be present in infected cells during virus replication. A subgenomic mRNA-specific RT-qPCR for SARS-CoV-2 was described in a manuscript submitted already at March 1st 2020 [31], which was coauthored by first and senior authors of the Charité protocol. Here, at the very latest, all WHO-recommended protocols should have been substantially changed.

In general, PCR may contribute to improve differential diagnostics, i.e., when applying multiplex testing for a broad range of pathogens in order to discriminate between distinct pulmonary infections, which often show a highly similar pathology. As is the case for any other laboratory assay, the outcome of the PCR test needs interpretation within the context of the patient's clinical presentation. As PCR represents a highly sensitive technique, it will be possible to detect both an underrepresented pathogen within a pathogen mixture, regularly present in a patient sample, as has been reported for two of the five first Covid-19 patients in Wuhan [3], and even remnants (nucleic acid fragments) of the pathogen in question after the immune system already got rid of it.

RT-qPCR can only support, but not replace medical differential diagnoses

To sum up, it is highly important that clinicians realize the key problems that are associated with PCR-based laboratory assays:

Firstly, there is a clear difference in the key question between clinical and epidemiological testing. While clinical testing aims at a high sensitivity in order to confirm or decline a suspected infection in a symptomatic individual, epidemiological testing aims at the specific detection of truly infectious individuals, which are able to spread the viral infection. As PCR is not able to detect or predict whether a positively tested individual will be infectious or not, it does not represent a “robust diagnostic tool.” Accordingly, PCR-based tests should never be used for surveilling an asymptomatic healthy population with the aim to “detect” nucleic acid sequences of SARS-CoV-2 or any other virus.

Secondly, the PCR test result can by no means replace a thorough medical diagnosis considering patient characteristics, i.e., symptoms, contact history, co-morbidities, drug history, age and Ct-value (see below). Covid-19 shares common symptoms of respiratory tract infections and, therefore, could not accurately diagnosed by a single distinct symptom or sign, as recently published by a Cochrane report [32].

Thirdly, even in the case in which a PCR test exhibits both high specificity and high sensitivity, there will be a huge number of false-positive and false-negative results, which are due to technical reasons (see below) and clinical reasons. As has been reported in a systematic review and meta-analysis [33], the infectious period of SARS-CoV-2 starts about two days after exposure and continues up to 12 days after onset of symptoms. By contrast, PCR may remain positive for up to 90 days [34]. Consequently, PCR-positive individuals are not identical with individuals that can effectively transmit the virus! This discrepancy becomes obvious in the group of positive tested, but asymptomatic individuals representing low initial target numbers and high Ct-values in the test readout. Here, the vast majority will not be infectious, but represent clinical false-positives [35]. For a comprehensive review on the problem of clinical false-positives and false-negatives, refer to Figure 2 in Verna et al. [36]. Rather, as recommended by both WHO and CDC, the PCR test will help the physician in confirming or declining an initial suspicion whether a symptomatic patient is suffering from a possible SARS-CoV-2 infection [37,38,39].

Ct-value correlates with target gene amount

The threshold cycle (Ct), also called quantification cycle (Cq), is the cycle number when the fluorescence of the amplified PCR product can be specifically detected above the background signal. It represents a measure of the amount of a specific nucleic acid sequence that was

present in the original sample. The lower the Ct-value, the more PCR product and thus the more target material was initially present.

As reverse transcription, priming conditions and secondary structures at the primer binding sites represent stochastic processes, the Ct-value may vary between different RT-qPCR runs and different laboratories. Therefore, reference genes of defined amounts must be included in order to measure relative quantification between various study groups. This represents a minimum requirement for a “robust diagnostic tool,” but inexplicably was not performed by the authors of the Charité protocol. In addition, absolute quantification of a defined virus number present in a specific sample requires qPCR methodology with a dilution series of known amounts of inactivated virus. Subsequently, the Ct-value of an unknown sample can be compared with the Ct-values of the dilution series and the virus number can be estimated to determine the viral copies per ml, the so-called viral load.

For SARS-CoV-2, Wölfel et al. [31] reported that a minimum of 10^6 RNA copies per ml are comparable with a viral load that is able to successfully infect a cell culture and thus is defined as potentially infectious. Jaafar et al. [40] compared 3790 positive RT-qPCR samples with positive cell cultures and reported that the virus can be extracted in 70%, 20% and 3% of the samples when applying Ct-values of 25, 30 and 35, respectively. Applying 45(!) PCR cycles, the Charité protocol was described to detect as little as four RNA copies per sample (approx. 10^3 RNA copies/ml) [8]. Some commercial test kits report a detection threshold of 10 RNA copies per sample [41]. This is roughly 10^3 - 10^5 -fold more sensitive than the infectious viral load, which is required to grow the virus in a cell culture setting. Thus, a positive PCR signal does per se not allow one to make inferences about a possible infectious viral load, if not related to a defined standard curve [42]. Low Ct-values (18-21) reflect approximately 10^5 - 10^6 RNA copies per ml sample. It is now well supported that samples with high cycle threshold (Ct > 25) do not contain enough genetic material to correlate with an infectious potential [17,43,44]. Stang and coworkers [44] reported that Ct-values between symptomatic and asymptomatic subjects differed by more than four cycles (25.5 versus 29.6, respectively) and concluded that the Ct-value for defining potentially infectious individuals should be lowered from 30 to 25. Based on our routine experience with real-time quantitative PCR (hundreds of tests diagnostically used since 2006), we adopted the following routine criterion to evaluate the clinical significance of the measured SARS-CoV-2 viral load: unremarkable positivity from 10^1 - 10^2 copies/ml (Ct 40-37); moderate positivity from 10^3 - 10^4 copies/ml (Ct 35-27); remarkable positivity above 10^5 copies/ml (Ct < 25).

Target gene number and specificity

To reliably detect a specific virus by RT-qPCR, either a well-defined, highly specific and conserved target region (i.e., our 5'-UTR assay) or in case this is not possible, more than one

gene or specific sequence of that virus must be targeted by distinct sets of specific primers. The Charité protocol [8] specified three target genes to detect SARS-CoV-2, namely the E-gene, the RdRp-gene (which is the ORF-1ab gene coding for the RdRp protein) and the N-gene. The primers selected for the Charite E-gene target were defined as specific for the whole Sarbeco-group of coronaviruses including SARS and Bat-derived Sarbecoviruses and thus clearly fails to fulfill the requirements for a specific SARS-CoV-2 detection by design and thus was excluded from analysis in a manuscript testing all WHO-recommended RT-qPCR protocols [45]. Further, one probe from the RdRp target is defined as “Pan-Sarbeco” as well. Despite this design, which intends to be not exclusively specific for the new SARS-CoV-2 virus, these targets all have their own absolute specificity and error rate (**Table 2**). The number of false-positive results can be calculated for each individual gene and also for a combination of the genes. In brief, the risk of false-positives for non-specific primers like in the Charite protocol depends on the number of target genes tested, namely the less of the target genes are tested, the more false-positive results will be generated. It is therefore completely incomprehensible why the WHO, during the course of the pandemic, recommended to reduce the number of the given target genes without improving the specificity of the primer design. In the original Charité protocol (published January 13th 2020), it was recommended to test for three genes (E-gene, RdRp-gene, N-gene) [6], which then could have limited the number of false-positives. However, in the 1st modification (published January 17th 2020), PCR-detection of the N-gene (the most specific and in dilution series most sensitive [42] and therefore less often positive target) was omitted [9]. Further, with the 2nd modification (published March 2nd 2020), it was recommended that “in areas, where Covid-19 virus is widely spread, a simpler algorithm might be adopted, in which for example screening by RT-qPCR of a single discriminatory target (i.e., the E-gene) is considered sufficient” [47]. These modifications - especially the final recommendation to test for the highly unspecific E-gene as the sole target – will definitely have increased the risk of false-positives thus driving the case numbers, but also could have influenced the number of false-negatives [48,49,50].

Table 2 Specificity of the SARS-CoV-2 target genes E, RdRp and N, as evaluated in a round robin test by the German Institute Instand [46].

Target gene	No. of tests	Specificity of cell culture (without viral RNA) [%]	Specificity of related Coronavirus (HCoV229E) [%]	Percent [%]	Mean absolute specificity	Mean error rate (1 – mean abs. spec.)
SARS-CoV-2						
E-gene	24	99.46	95.17	97.31	0.9731	0.0269
RdRp-gene	13	97.80	90.66	94.23	0.9423	0.0577
N-gene	21	98.20	87.95	93.08	0.9308	0.0692

Disputable primer design

Any reliable RT-qPCR assay critically depends on the quality of primers designed to amplify the target sequence. For diagnostic purposes, it is essential that primers are 100% specific for the target of interest in order to avoid cross-reactivity with sequences of closely related genes and thus virus variants [26]. When two or more primer-sets are applied, amplification efficiencies per primer-set may nevertheless be distinct. This may result in different assay sensitivities due to differences in priming efficiency associated with secondary structure or stability [9,22]. The Charité protocol describes primers containing up to six unspecified positions. The unspecified positions result in the design of several different alternative primer sequences (two distinct RdRp_SARSr_F primers + 8 distinct RdRp_SARS_P1 probes + 4 distinct RdRp_SARSr_R). In addition, one of the N-primers (sequence GCAGACGTGGTCCAGAACAAA) shares 10 bases with a sequence of human chromosome-1 (sequence GCAGACTCTGAGGGGATGCCA), of which six bases are located at the 3' end and therefore pose a high risk of unspecific priming [20]. However, the RdRp reverse primer of the Charité protocol is even more problematic, since it is 100% identical to a sequence present on human chromosome-18 [20]. This may generate unintended PCR amplification even in the absence of any SARS-CoV-2 sequences. In addition, the RdRp-gene has been reported to be problematic in the sense of having the lowest rate of positive detection and highest Ct-value [51,52]. Another important aspect of PCR primer design is the annealing temperature (T_m), which critically depends on the GC-content of the primer sequence. The lower the T_m , the higher the risk of false-positive results. Further, the T_m of a primer pair should be very similar, preferably not further apart than 2 °C [53]. Several of the Charité protocol primers violate this principle (for details, see [20]). For instance, the 26 bp E-gene forward primer reveals a GC content of only 34.6 % resulting in an almost 10 °C T_m difference with the 23 bp reverse primer exhibiting a GC content of 45.4 %.

Validation of generated amplicons by sequencing is mandatory

Assessment of the absolute virus amount in a patient sample, which is necessary to correlate the Ct-value with the infectious viral load estimated by cell culture, requires quantitative PCR, which is different from qualitative PCR [27]. Qualitative PCR generates a defined amplicon, which normally is detected by size-dependent analysis in an agarose gel and can then be used as the template for sequencing analysis. In quantitative PCR, a Ct-value is generated, which represents the kinetics of an accumulated fluorescing signal that correlates with probe degradation. Consequently, no confirmation of the correct amplification of the target gene is possible in this process. Especially for newly designed protocols, amplification is usually followed by agarose gel and sequencing analysis in order to confirm the amplified sequence.

Although whole or at least partial genome sequencing is recommended by the WHO [54,55,56], the authors of the Charité protocol did not include this important confirmation step, i.e., Sanger sequencing. Hence, the specificity of the primers and probes used in this protocol to produce a reliable target-specific amplification has never been shown [8].

However, as early as in April 2020, it was known within the scientific community that the Charité protocol suffered from specificity problems of unknown origin [57]. Even under standardized laboratory conditions, Corman and coworkers [8] themselves reported that four positive samples were negative after re-testing representing the classical example of false-positives or random laboratory contaminations with PCR products due to handling issues. The fact that the authors explained their false-positives indeed as “handling issues,” which even occurred in the very beginning of the Charité protocol in an experienced laboratory setting, raises serious questions on the contamination rate in large laboratories during mass testing in often new established commercial labs.

Subsequently, Muenchhoff and coworkers [58] performed a proficiency test for inter-laboratory performance evaluation submitting a dilution series of a SARS-CoV-2 PCR-positive sample to seven participating laboratories. All laboratories reported that all samples were negative at a $Ct \geq 32$. The authors reported the following: “Based on computation using Primer Express v3.0 (Applied Biosystems, Dreieich, Germany) annealing temperatures were predicted to be 64 °C for the RdRp forward and 51 °C for the RdRp reverse primer of the Charité protocol. This temperature difference may result in reduced PCR efficiency.” Despite these facts, the authors concluded the following: “The majority of RT-PCR assays for SARS-CoV-2 examined detected five RNA copies per reaction reflecting a high sensitivity and their suitability for screening purposes worldwide.” This conclusion is valid, when PCR sensitivity is considered only. However, this remarkable high sensitivity of the RT-qPCR bears the risk of amplifying even small residues of a past infection, which is not suitable for a diagnostic tool with major repercussions for positive and negative tested individuals. Here, the specificity is far more important [59]. High specificity for the target genes in combination with sensitive Ct-values (≤ 25) are the features of a robust and reliable PCR test (as already detailed above).

Another well-known diagnostic challenge is the occurrence of mutations and new virus variants, which require regular validation and possibly primer re-design in order to avoid potential primer-sample mismatches. This has been demonstrated by Osorio and coworkers, who aligned 1825 SARS-CoV-2 genome sequences deposited in the GISAID database (March 2020) against the Wuhan-Hu-1 reference sequence (NC_045512). Subsequently, they annotated in the alignments the binding sites of 33 oligonucleotides shared by the WHO for the use in RT-qPCR and found that approx. 79% of the analyzed primer-binding sequences exhibited mutations in at least one target gene [60].

In addition, our own NGS data generated in the Czech Republic from October 2020 to January 2021 confirmed that validation of a PCR-based diagnostic test by sequencing is mandatory, not only during the initial phase of establishment, but also on a regular basis during the following time. The necessity for such an approach was shown quite plainly by our NGS data, which revealed that each of the three individual waves culminating in the Czech Republic during October 2020, November 2020 and December 2020/January 2021 was genomically different. Although SARS-CoV-2 reveals a high mutation rate, with our 5'-UTR assay, we were able to reliably identify all circulating strains, i.e., alpha, beta, gamma, delta, omicron. Interestingly, mutations found in the September 2020 wave were not present in the directly following November 2020 and December 2020 waves. This discrepancy has become fully obvious with the omicron variant, which reportedly lacks direct evolutionary connection to any of the previous SARS-CoV-2 variants [61]. This appears to be rather unusual, given the fact that the Czech Republic had implemented all restriction measures, namely lockdown, massively restricted traveling, social distancing and facial masks. In this respect, the Czech Republic territory behaved as a genetically confined, isolated population that would not support such a SARS-CoV-2 diversity. Namely, subsequent waves, originating in a confined area, should carry all the mutations of its predecessor and could only add some more mutations during its evolution. However, this was not the case, the disparity being most prominent between the September 2020 and the November 2020 SARS-CoV-2 strain, when the November wave "lost" 14 mutations that were present in the preceding September wave.

Good laboratory practice requires a SOP

The high sensitivity of PCR-based technology goes along with a severe bottleneck in the performance. Even in case of a 100% test specificity, tantamount to a false-positive rate of 0%, the outcome solely refers to a lack of reaction with sequences other than the selected target sequences. However, this analytical specificity calculated in certified laboratories cannot be equated to specificity in real-world testing, where contaminants, which are also amplified exponentially, and handling errors by untrained personnel will unavoidably result in the generation of false-positives. For example, Layfield and colleagues [62] reported false-positive specimens in a plate map that were located adjacent to high viral load specimens ($Ct < 20$). Moreover, when the positivity rate approaches the false-positive rate, the reliability of a positive test result falls to near zero. This is especially important when the prevalence is low, as there are more uninfected than infected individuals. In this scenario, small changes in specificity will have a much larger impact on the probability that an individual testing positive has the infection than variations in sensitivity [63].

To avoid errors inherent to any laboratory analysis, detection procedures always come together with a reliable SOP. The RT-qPCR test is only suitable as diagnostic tool for virus

detection, if it is standardized and controlled on all levels, so that erroneous results can be excluded to a reasonable extent. For the detection of SARS-CoV-2, the SOP should include an anonymized panel of test samples containing inactivated virus material made available by an external provider (i.e., a reference laboratory), a negative sample and samples with closely related virus in order to check for specificity (these samples must remain negative). Ideally, the SOP should also contain a dilution series of inactivated virus to determine the sensitivity of the test (with Ct-value corresponding with the infectious viral load). This can only be achieved by designing a SOP with a worldwide validity, which is experimentally validated in a so-called round robin test (see **Footnote 1**). That a SOP is mandatory becomes obvious from studies in Germany coordinated by Instand, an organization, which grants certificates for good laboratory practice. Their round robin test to validate the RT-qPCR, involving 488 laboratories, revealed considerable problems [46]. Of note, during an ongoing round robin test, three of seven samples were excluded from the blind panel due to “urgent requests from Germany and abroad to reveal the properties of the samples to be tested before the end of the extended submission period, i.e., before April 28, 2020, so that laboratories can improve their test method in the short term in case of possible incorrect measurements.” Intervention in a round robin procedure is very unusual and the report cannot be regarded to represent an independent external validation procedure of the participating laboratories. An additional concern, even in this controlled round robin test procedure with the samples already prepared and a reduced test scope, is sample mix-ups that occurred in 24 laboratories, which interestingly enough always affected the same SARS-CoV-2 positive probe with the control probe containing the common cold coronavirus HCoV229E [46]. Finally, it was noticed that detection of the target genes showed enormous variation between laboratories with respect to Ct-values. For example, the Ct-values for the same diluted sample of SARS-CoV-2 (sample number 340061) ranged between 15-40 for the E-gene, 20-40.7 for the N-gene and 19.5-42.8 for the RdRp-gene [65]. Together, these data impressively demonstrate an extreme lack of test standardization within the participating, certified laboratories. As there is no worldwide (or at least EU-wide or USA-wide) SOP, we can only imagine the enormous variation generated in laboratories detecting “SARS-CoV-2 RNA” in real patient samples.

Footnote 1

In order to minimize the likelihood of incorrect test results, each RT-qPCR run must include the following internal controls in addition to patient samples, e.g.:

- a blank swab to exclude contamination during sample collection;
- a RNA extraction control to ensure correct RNA isolation;
- a “waterproof” as internal negative control;
- a reference gene (e.g., human RNaseP) as internal positive control;
- positive controls of inactivated SARS-CoV-2 isolated from cell culture supernatants to correlate the Ct-value with the copy number of the replication-competent infectious viral load, e.g., by plaque assays [64]. This includes:
 - a concentration that corresponds with the infectious viral load (10^7) with a Ct < 30 in all amplified target genes and

- a probe that corresponds with a non-infectious concentration (e.g., 5×10^5) in order to define the Ct-value above which RT-qPCR gain negative results;
- cross-reactivity control (must remain negative), e.g., “normal seasonal flu” Coronavirus lines, such as OC43 and 229E, which like SARS-CoV-2 positive controls have been inactivated at a viral load of 10^7 .

Conclusion

Violation of principles of good scientific practice enabled politicians to apply non-evidence-based medicine on entire populations

The Charité protocol represents an infringement of all internationally recognized principles of good scientific practice (**Footnote 2**). Firstly, the primers used for RT-qPCR were forwarded to testing companies, i.e., Labor Berlin and Tib Molbiol, and made commercially available as Light Mix Diagnostic Test Kits, i.e., LightMix® Modular SARS-CoV-2/Covid-19, RdRp; LightMix® Modular SARS-CoV-2/Covid-19, E-gene; Tib Molbiol, Roché Diagnostics. Secondly, the test protocol was published online as a WHO-guideline prior to peer-review and publication in Eurosurveillance. It was only then that it underwent a rapid 24-hour peer-review, apparently justified by the imminent pandemic. Nevertheless, there were only six deaths worldwide on January 21st 2020, the day the manuscript was submitted [12]. Furthermore, the Tib Molbiol LightMix Kit was already available in Slovenia a week before publication of the Charité protocol [10]. At that time, not a single case of SARS-CoV-2 was documented in Europe. Thirdly, two of the authors are members of the Eurosurveillance Editorial Board, another is the managing director of Tib Molbiol, while yet another is a senior researcher at GenExpress and a scientific advisor for Tib Molbiol - none of these potential conflicts of interest were disclosed when submitting the manuscript.

The neglect of internationally recognized principles of good scientific practice prompted the publication of a severely flawed laboratory assay. Subsequently, RT-qPCR positive outcomes were equated with “Covid cases” even in the absence of any disease symptoms. From a scientific perspective, the daily reports of so-called “new cases” or “new infections” did not make any sense, since it was neither established whether they were “new”, nor that they were “infections.” The high sensitivity of PCR enables the detection of viral fragments of any origin, but PCR cannot diagnose “cases” or “infections.” Indeed, more than half of the positive test outcomes are not likely to be infectious [40]. Nevertheless, governments implemented quarantines of healthy people and installed lockdowns with significant collateral damages on societies and economies worldwide based on a highly questionable RT-qPCR test.

In summary, positive test results comprise a mixture of true Covid cases (i.e., contact with SARS-CoV-2 at least 9 days ago, probably infectious), untrue cases (i.e., contact with virus or virus fragments less than 9 days, probably not infectious) and false cases (healthy, for sure not infectious). The distribution of these three categories depends on laboratory distinctions,

kits used, skills of the technicians, etc. We thus strongly argue against using the RT-qPCR technology to measure “cases” or “infections” without appropriate and independent old-fashioned physician-made diagnosis. We conclude that the application of this technology as a population-wide mass testing instrument unnecessarily exaggerated and prolonged the SARS-CoV-2 situation.

Footnote 2

Internationally recognized principles of good scientific practice include:

- formal aspects, e.g., thorough review of research results by independent referees before publication and expression of any kind of existing conflict of interest by all co-authors, such as project funding by the pharmaceutical industry,
- research aspects, e.g., the implementation of a valid protocol, including positive and negative controls, as well as the confirmation of results and deployment of appropriate and sound techniques,
- quality assurance and the establishment of standards. The latter of which are of particular importance upon the development of new methods or diagnostic tests, especially when a test result may decide upon patient treatment.

Lack of transparency was and still is an omnipresent companion of the crisis ending up by causing more harm than good

Two BMJ Editorials argued that during Covid-19 politicians and governments were suppressing science to accelerate the commercial availability of diagnostics and treatments [66,67]. While in light of an imminent “killer-virus pandemic,” the publication and marketing of a suboptimal RT-qPCR test for SARS-CoV-2 detection may be defended, any errors and inappropriate scientific standards discovered after publication must be reported and corrected immediately. A request to retract the Charité protocol based on ten formal and technical concerns was submitted to the Eurosurveillance editorial board in November 2020, but never received serious consideration [20,68]. The request was declined in an online statement based on five undisclosed expert reviews, although none of the concerns were addressed appropriately [69]. Moreover, an addendum containing 20 published papers supporting these concerns was not even mentioned. The subsequent appeal to disclose the peer-review reports of the five peer reviewers was declined by the Eurosurveillance editorial board and thus violated key scientific standards that normally guarantee a transparent peer-review process to enable an honest scientific dialogue. Why they did not choose to inform the scientific community about conceivable shortcomings and pitfalls of the Charité protocol remains elusive.

Finally, the decision-making processes of the WHO lacks transparency, as twelve years after the swine flu, it is still unclear why the WHO modified the definition of a pandemic. According to the old definition, it would not have been possible to declare Covid-19 a pandemic. It is also incomprehensible why the WHO did not immediately publish an English version of the RT-qPCR test developed by the CCDC, but rather published a different European test. Further, why did the WHO not immediately report on the importance of the Ct-value and interpretation of the RT-qPCR test results when the PCR technology was adopted as the “gold standard” to

detect SARS-CoV-2? Why did they do so only one year after the onset of the pandemic? [54] If the lack of transparency is not due to scientific ignorance, which we find a reasonable conclusion, it might result from an undesirable intrusion of politics in science. If so, this would be disturbing. At all costs, science must stay free from political and religious ideologies, from dogmas and from financial interests.

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Authors' contributions

UK, SP, PB, KS: Study design. SP: NGS analysis. RJK, RL, KS: Review design. All authors were involved in reviewing the literature and writing the manuscript.

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Competing interest declaration

RL, Erasmus MC and BioCoS, has signed a joint ownership agreement related to SARS-CoV-2 detection methods. All other authors declare: no support from any organization for the submitted work; no financial relationships with any organizations that might have an interest in the submitted work in the previous three years; no other relationships or activities that could appear to have influenced the submitted work.

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Figure 1 SARS-CoV-2 NGS whole genome sequencing data of three randomly selected representative genomes collected between September 2020 and April 2021 in the Czech Republic. **A** Individual SARS-CoV-2 autumn 2020 waves are highlighted in red (September 2020), blue (November 2020) and yellow (December 2020). Graph has been adopted from www.worldometers.info open source. **B** Table shows (from 5' to 3') the wave-specific SARS-CoV-2 mutations found throughout the respective genomes (Orf1ab, S, Orf3a, M, Orf8). Mutations are translated into amino acids and highlighted by a black "x". Black boxes highlight those mutations that were present in the September 2020 SARS-CoV-2 strain, but were absent in the directly following November 2020 SARS-CoV-2 strain. A similar pattern is discernible with the December 2020 SARS-CoV-2 strain (already dubbed as "British", or later on as "Alpha"). Given the fact that at that time the Czech Republic territory, from the genetic point of view, corresponded to a genetically confined area, the observation that the individual strains were not directly genetically interrelated, is rather astounding.

